

dealers and well connected businessmen, in turn sell these products across India and export them overseas at hefty prices.

The tribal artists at the bottom of these trade make next to nothing to support their livelihood. This has been the case in both pre colonial as well as post colonial India; where tribal artists have been ruthlessly exploited and cheated disproportionately; and this needs to change. There is an urgent need to provide financial support to tribal artists who have been engaged in practising and protecting their indigenous artworks against all odds for several past generations. Both government and non-government agencies operating in tribal dominated areas need to organize the artists into self-help groups or small

indigenous cooperatives. Such agencies need to buy and/or collect artworks from tribal communities across the country against genuine prices fixed by the government. The products collected could then be sold or auctioned or exported for higher profits. A percentage of the net profit should be returned to the indigenous self-help groups or indigenous cooperatives to fund their local economic development or economic empowerment. Tribal art is an unique heritage of India; and hence needs proper conservation of these unique artworks and protection of the tribal artist who has helped keeping the indigenous art alive and breathing in modern India.

Photo credit: Saikat Kumar Basu

STATUS AND PROSPECTS OF STINGLESS BEE IN JHANSI DISTRICT OF BUNDELKHAND REGION

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Stingless bees are the most abundant and diverse group of social insects. They play a significant cultural and economic role and are active pollinators. Their primary function is to pollinate both cultivated and wild flowers, making them vital to the preservation of biodiversity and food security. They are essential to preserving the diversity of plant species. Stingless bees are also known as dammar bees' with additional local names in different Indian states such as, e.g., putka (Sikkim), ngap siwor and ngap hamang (Khasi language), cherutheneecha and arakki (Kerala), Tenetigalu (Andhra Pradesh), Mulijenu, Mujanatejenu, Misrijenu, Nasarujenu, and Kirujenu (Karnataka). Since stingless bees are among the most economically significant and physiologically fascinating insect groups, bee scientists worldwide are paying close attention to these insects (Hymenoptera: Apidae: Meliponini). They produce 200–500 g of honey, which is more valuable medicinally than honey produced by Apis bees. In the world, there are thought to be more than 500 species of stingless bees. The two genera into which stingless bees can be divided are Melipona and Trigona. There are 22 species of stingless

bees known to exist in India. They are classified into three genera: Tetragonula, Lisotrigona, and Lepidotrigona. Tetragonula are tiny, dark bees that live in cavities such as tree hollows.

A naturally occurring species of bee found on practically every continent is the stingless bee. They are typically built in pre-existing cavities, such as termite and ant mounds, tree trunks, stone walls, wall corners, cracks, and other substrates created by humans. Its presence has been observed in India, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Kenya, Africa, America, Australia, Uruguay, Southeast Asia, Taiwan and Malaysia, Nepal. In India it is found in different states like Himachal Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Kerala, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Meghalaya, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, Tripura, Tamil Nadu, and north-eastern states. In Jhansi district of Uttar Pradesh, stingless bee presence has been observed in all nine blocks and through different surveys, foraging plants visited by a stingless bee are Portulaca (*Portulaca oleracea*), Rose (*Rosa spp.*), Crape myrtle (*Lagerstroemia indica*), Sun flower (*Helianthus annuus*), Hollyhock (*Alcea rosea*), Common mallow (*Malva sylvestris*), Pak choi (*Brassica rapa subsp. Chinensis*), Garlic vine (*Mansoa alliacea*), Dombey (*Dombeya spectabilis*), Brinjal (*Solanum melongena*), Hawaiian Ti Plant/ Good-Luck Plant (*Cordyline fruticosa*), Marguerite daisy (*Argyranthemum frutescens*) Curtain creeper (*Tarlmounia elliptica*), mango (*M. indica*), Strawberry (*Fragaria x ananassa*), Citrus

Crepe-myrtle

Sun flower

Paper flower

(*Citrus spp.*), Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*), and Cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*).

Throughout history, people have utilised this bee's honey extensively. This honey stands out due to its natural storage in the pot (cerumen), which enhances its therapeutic abilities and promotes better health overall. Stingless bee honey (SBH), pot-honey, sugarbag honey, kelulut honey, and meliponine honey are some of the names given to honey made by these bees. A number of useful products that the stingless bee produces, including propolis, or cerumen, honey, and pollen, can be used as a source of revenue for future generations.

In addition, stingless bees are crucial to the economy, culture, and ecology. For many tropical plants, both cultivated and natural, they serve as the primary pollinators. A vast array of medicinal benefits can be derived from stingless bee honey, such as anti-aging, wound healing, anti-viral/fungal, anti-inflammatory, anti-

cancer, and antioxidant qualities. One of the best natural remedies for wound healing, eye conditions, gastrointestinal system illnesses, neurological conditions, and infertility issues is stingless bee honey.

Despite their importance, stingless bees face numerous threats causing alarming population declines due to several factors in the regions such as the occurrence of heat waves, intense heat during summer, less foraging plants, and awareness regarding stingless bees is very poor. Moreover, stingless bees have a great cultural and traditional value therefore, in future much attention has to be given for the protection of stingless culture through the planting of new bee specific forest, planting of bee-friendly plants as avenue plants/tree in a home garden, roof garden, roadside, and in wasteland area. Besides this more research needs to be done for the conservation and identification of polleniferous and nectariferous plants preferred by these bees.